

Open Science Community Iraq (OSCI)

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Open Science Community Iraq (OSCI) is dedicated to fostering a collaborative space for exchanging open science practices and providing feedback on relevant policies and infrastructures.

Open Science Community Iraq

Who are we?

Welcome to the Open Science Community Iraq (OSCI), a pioneering initiative established to foster open science practices across Iraq's scientific landscape. Our mission is to facilitate accessible, transparent, and collaborative scientific research, thereby contributing to global scientific dialogue and local innovation. At OSCI, we are committed to advancing open access to scientific data and publications, advocating for supportive policies, and nurturing a culture of open scientific exchange. Through workshops, collaborations, and advocacy, our impact extends to researchers, educators, and policymakers. Our team, comprising dedicated professionals with diverse scientific backgrounds, is the driving force behind our endeavors. We invite researchers, institutions, and all advocates of open science to join us in this transformative journey, shaping a future where knowledge is open and shared freely. Connect with us to be a part of this exciting movement.

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Open Science Revolution

To expand on the concept of the "Open Science Revolution" in the context of Iraq and globally, we can explore several key aspects:

Definition of Open Science: Open Science refers to a movement aimed at making scientific research, data, and dissemination accessible to all levels of an inquiring society, amateur or professional. It encompasses practices such as publishing open research, campaigning for open access, encouraging scientists to practice open notebook science, and generally making it easier to publish and communicate scientific knowledge.

Global Impact of Open Science: Globally, Open Science is revolutionizing the way research is conducted and shared. It fosters collaboration among scientists across the world, accelerates the pace of discovery, and increases the transparency and reliability of research. By making data and research findings openly available, it ensures that scientific knowledge can be built upon more efficiently and effectively.

Open Science in Iraq: In the context of Iraq, the Open Science movement can be particularly transformative. Iraq has a rich history of scientific inquiry and education, but like many countries, it faces challenges such as limited access to resources, political instability, and economic constraints. Embracing Open Science can help Iraqi researchers gain access to a broader array of scientific resources, collaborate with international peers, and contribute more effectively to global scientific endeavors.

Role of the Open Science Community Iraq: The "Open Science Community Iraq" could play a crucial role in this revolution. It could act as a platform for Iraqi scientists to share their research, access international scientific resources, and collaborate with peers both within and outside Iraq. The community could also advocate for policies that support open science practices, organize training and workshops, and contribute to building a sustainable open science infrastructure in Iraq.

Long-Term Vision: The ultimate goal of the Open Science movement in Iraq would be to integrate the country more fully into the global scientific community, foster a culture of transparency and collaboration in research, and utilize open science to address local and global challenges. This could lead to significant advancements in science and technology within Iraq and contribute to the country's overall development.

Challenges and Opportunities: While the movement offers significant benefits, it also poses challenges, especially in resource-limited settings like Iraq. These include the need for infrastructure to support open access, training for researchers in open science practices, and policies that encourage and protect open scientific work. However, these challenges also present opportunities for development, international collaboration, and innovation in the field of science and technology.

In summary, the "Open Science Revolution," particularly in Iraq, represents a pivotal shift in how scientific research is conducted and shared. It holds the promise of greater inclusivity, collaboration, and advancement in the scientific world.

What is Open Science?

Open Science describes an ongoing movement in a way research is performed, researchers collaborate, knowledge is shared, and science is organized. It affects the whole research cycle and its stakeholders and enhances science by facilitating more transparency, openness, networking, and collaboration.

Why Join Our Community?

Learn about Open Science practices through our Workshops. Support to lead your project, and provide more visibility and discoverability for your work. OSCI helps you to get connected with like-minded people from other communities that adopt Open Science practices (e.g. Turing Way, Carpentries, ArabR, ...).
Subscribe to our [OSCI mailing list](#).

Who Can Join?

We welcome everyone regardless of their knowledge of Open Science. Please fill out [this form](#) with instructions on how to join.

Open Science Community Iraq (OSCI)

Aims and Scopes

The Open Science Community Iraq (OSCI) has specific aims and scopes tailored to the unique needs and context of Iraq's scientific community:

1-Promoting Open Access to Scientific Research: OSCI's primary aim could be to facilitate open access to scientific papers, data, and methodologies, ensuring that Iraqi researchers and the global community can freely access and utilize this information.

2-Fostering Collaboration and Networking: The organization might focus on building networks among Iraqi scientists and with the international scientific community. This could involve organizing conferences, workshops, and collaborative projects, promoting the exchange of ideas and resources.

3-Supporting Research

Transparency and Reproducibility:

OSCI may aim to enhance the transparency and reproducibility of research conducted in Iraq. This can be achieved by advocating for the use of open notebooks, pre-registration of studies, and sharing of raw data and experimental procedures.

4- Capacity Building and Education:

Given the challenges in resources and infrastructure, a key focus might be on building capacity in open science practices among Iraqi researchers. This could include training programs, educational resources, and support for adopting open science tools and methodologies.

5- Policy Advocacy:

OSCI could work towards influencing science policy in Iraq to support open science principles. This might involve advocating for government and institutional policies that mandate or encourage open access publishing, data sharing, and other open science practices.

6- Addressing Local and Global

Challenges: The community might aim to leverage open science to address specific challenges faced in Iraq, such as environmental issues, health crises, or technological development, while also contributing to global scientific efforts.

7-Promoting Science

Communication and Public Engagement:

OSCI could also focus on enhancing public engagement with science, helping to communicate scientific knowledge to a broader audience, and encouraging public involvement in scientific discourse and decision-making.

What is FAIR data?

The Four Basics of FAIR:

Findable: i.e. discoverable with metadata, identifiable and locatable by means of a standard identification mechanism.

Accessible: i.e. always available and obtainable; even if the data is restricted, the metadata is open.

Interoperable: i.e. both syntactically parseable and semantically understandable, allowing data exchange and reuse between researchers, institutions, organisations or countries

Reusable: i.e. sufficiently described and shared with the least restrictive licences, allowing the widest reuse possible and the least cumbersome integration with other data sources.

Open Science Practices of OSCI

OPEN SOURCE

Open source software is a code that is designed to be publicly accessible. Prime examples include Linux, Firefox & Android

OPEN LICENSE

Open Work is protected by Open License, which states how the work can be used, modified, adopted and commercialised

OPEN EDUCATIONAL RESOURCES

They are any learning and research materials that reside in the public domain or under an open license.

OPEN HARDWARE

Open source hardware is a hardware that is built based on principles analogous to open source software

OPEN ACCESS

Open Access refers to online, free of cost access to peer reviewed scientific content with limited copyright and licensing restrictions

Our Team

The Open Science Community Iraq (OSCI) team, established in 2023, comprises a dynamic group of professionals dedicated to advancing open science principles in Iraq. The team, made up of experts from various scientific disciplines, works tirelessly to promote accessibility, transparency, and collaboration in scientific research. Key objectives include increasing open access to scientific data, enhancing research quality, and fostering international collaboration. The OSCI team actively organizes workshops, participates in global initiatives, and advocates for policy changes supporting open science. Their efforts have notably contributed to a growing awareness and adoption of open science practices in the Iraqi scientific community. Looking forward, the team is focused on expanding its reach, developing more comprehensive training programs, and engaging more actively in global open science dialogues.

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Strategic Event Planning for Enhancing the Impact of Open Science Community Iraq (OSCI)

Upcoming Events

For the Open Science Community Iraq (OSCI), planning a variety of events can greatly enhance its impact and outreach. Here are some suggestions for upcoming events:

- **Open Science Workshops and Seminars:**

These workshops are crucial for educating researchers, students, and academics about open science practices, including open-access publishing, data sharing, and research reproducibility. They are fundamental for building a strong foundation in open science principles.

- **Research Data Management Training:**

Training sessions focused on effective research data management are essential. They ensure that data is FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable), which is a cornerstone of open science.

- **Policy Roundtables:**

Roundtable discussions with policymakers, academics, and industry experts can greatly influence the development and implementation of open science policies in Iraq. These discussions are key to creating an environment that supports and sustains open science practices.

- **Public Science Talks and Community Engagement Events:**

Engaging with the broader public is vital for increasing general awareness and support for open science. These events can help bridge the gap between the scientific community and the public, fostering a broader understanding and appreciation of science.

Get in touch: